

Synthesis of natrolite using the hydrothermal apparatus^ψ

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Manuscript received 21 August 2006, accepted 11 September 2006

Abstract : Natrolite (Na₂O.Al₂O₃.3SiO₂.2H₂O) was synthesized using hydrothermal apparatus at temperatures 200, 250, 300 and 350 °C and pressures 500 bar and 1000 bar. It was observed that the extent of formation of natrolite, as revealed by X-ray diffraction studies, increases with pressure in the temperature range 200 to 300 °C and then it decreases. When the pressure was kept at 750 bar and temperature varied from 225 to 275 °C, the extent of natrolite formation increases linearly. The percentage of crystallinity was also calculated from X-ray diffraction data. The FTIR spectra of synthesized natrolites at different temperatures and pressures were recorded by KBr wafer technique and different bands have been assigned.

Keywords : Natrolite, hydrothermal.

Zeolites are crystalline, hydrated aluminosilicates of alkali and alkaline earth cations, having infinite three dimensional structures. These class of inorganic materials have attracted wide scientific interest and a large number of publications dealing with zeolite science and technology appeared in literature¹.

Natrolite is one of the most Na-rich rock forming zeolite minerals. The wide spread occurrence of natrolite is related to the fact that it appears to be stable over a considerable range of temperature and pressure conditions. The characteristic needle-like natrolite is formed not only during burial diagenesis of volcanoclastic sediments and very low grade metamorphism of lavas, as is observed with many zeolites, but is also formed in saline, alkaline lakes at the surface of the earth as well as in pegmatitic and hydrothermal veins around alkaline intrusive complexes and as phenocryst phase in silica deficient igneous rocks². Understanding of phase relations involving natrolite is thus critical for interpretation and modeling of mineral paragenesis in a number of geologic environments.

In the present work an attempt has been made to synthesize natrolite using hydrothermal apparatus and to study the characteristic of synthesized natrolite by XRD and FTIR techniques.

Results and discussion

The percentage crystallinity was calculated as the sum of the peak heights of the unknown materials divided by the sum of the peak heights of a standard material that has been assumed to be 100% crystalline³

$$\% \text{ Crystallinity} = \frac{\text{Sum of the peak heights of unknown material}}{\text{Sum of the peak heights of standard material}} \times 100$$

The percentage of the intensity yield and crystallinity are shown in Table 1.

The X-ray results showed that at pressure 500 bar and temperature 200 to 300 °C the intensity of the X-ray diffraction peaks were increased, but at the same pressure on increasing temperature to 350 °C, the intensity decreases. The process was repeated at the same tem-

^ψPresented in 41st Annual Convention of Chemists, New Delhi, 2004.

Table 1. X-Rays data of samples at different pressure and temperature

Pressure (bar)	Temp. (°C)	Intensity	Yield	Crystallinity
500	200	38.82	46.86	95.38
	250	42.15	46.91	95.63
	300	49.40	46.76	94.97
	350	38.42	46.85	95.63
1000	200	41.40	45.88	95.60
	250	60.28	48.87	95.96
	300	63.97	48.85	96.19
	350	55.13	49.15	95.31
750	225	51.50	47.92	95.72
	275	61.42	48.90	95.94

peratures by applying 1000 bar pressure. In this case the intensity of the peaks were more than that at 500 bar pressure but mode of the graph is same as 500 bar pressure i.e. intensity increased from 200 to 300 °C but intensity decreased at temperature 350 °C (Fig. 1). However, when the process was repeated at temperatures 225 and 275 °C by applying pressure 750 bar, the graph shows a straight line.

The XRD peak intensity reflects the extent of natrolite formation (Fig. 1).

The natrolite formation has been suggested⁴ to take place as follows :

Fig. 1. The intensity of X-ray peak of natrolite at different temperatures at pressures (♦) 500 bar and (■) 1000 bar.

The Fourier transform infrared spectra of synthetic natrolite were recorded in the range 500 to 4000 cm⁻¹ using KBr wafar technique. All sample spectra show major peaks in the range 500 to 1500 cm⁻¹. Zeolites generally show the same aluminosilicate (Al-Si) frame work. The IR spectra of all samples show additional peaks in the region 3200–3900 cm⁻¹ which confirms the formation of natrolite⁵. Bands : 761–785 (νT.O. sym); 985–1039 (νT.O. assy); 1661–1684 (δH-O-H) and 3200–3900 (νSi-OH, νAl-OH modes, νOH).

Experimental

In order to synthesize natrolite, Na₂CO₃ (S.D. Fine) was used as the source for Na₂O and the natural quartz (SiO₂) was crushed in the presence of acetone. Then a mixture crushed quartz (SiO₂) (52.36%); Na₂O (18%) and Al₂O₃ (29.62%) (S.D. Fine) was prepared and grinded together to obtain a homogeneous mixture in agate mortar and poured in a platinum crucible. The crucible was then placed in a furnace (700–1000 °C). The heating resulted in the formation of a glass like compound with refractive index 1.54.

The substance was crushed and transferred to platinum capsules and then water was injected in each capsule. Then these four platinum capsules, after sealing, were placed in the hydrothermal apparatus to heat them at pressure 1000 bar for 65 h. In a different set of experiment the platinum capsule were heated respectively at same temperature for same duration with reduced pressure 500 bar. Two more samples were prepared in the same way and were heated at 225 and 275 °C respectively at pressure 750 bar. The hydrothermal apparatus (Model HR-IB-2, LECO Corp., U.S.), FTIR FILA-2000, ABB-Canada) and X-ray diffractometer (Model D/Max-2200 PC, Rigaku Corp.) were used in this work. The X-ray work was done in which scanning angle was varied from 5–60°. Various intensity of the samples were identified with the help of ASTM card.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Prof. Alok K. Gupta, Director, National Center of Experimental Mineralogy and Petrology, University of Allahabad, for providing laboratory facilities.

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